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CHALLENGES AND POSSIBILITIES IN THE EDUCATION OF STUDENTS WITH DEAFNESS: EXPERIENCE REPORT DURING A PANDEMIC

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ABSTRACT

In recent years, we did not imagine that approaching others would be a health risk, and it was necessary to maintain social distance. This pandemic brought many challenges and new possibilities, as technologies were able to reach where our presence would not be possible. In view of this, a guiding question arises: how was it possible to help people with deafness during the pandemic in the educational process, where there were often communicative problems within the family? The theme chosen aims to present some activities aimed at the use of the Brazilian Sign Language (Libras), benefiting the deaf and their families. For the development of this work, an Innovative Pedagogy was thought (Freire, 1996) and in the words of Mahatma Gandhi: "Be the change you want to see in the world".